

PLASMONIC NANOPARTICLE INTEGRATION WITH SI BACK CONTACT SOLAR CELLS

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ABSTRACT: This work analyses the advantages and disadvantages of strategies for the integration of silver nanoparticle (Ag NP) based plasmonic structures in Interdigitated Back Contact Solar Cells (IBC). The strategies studied consist in placing Ag NPs on either the front or the rear surface of the cell, or embedding them in an antireflection coating. It is shown that in all cases NPs give rise to light trapping which increases spectral response. It is also found that front surface NPs lead to unavoidable Fano interference losses which lead to a net decrease in photocurrent. The placing of NPs on the rear surface eliminated this problem, yielding a net increase in photocurrent. The successful implementation of rear surface NPs is described with regards to avoiding associated shunt resistance paths, and the application of the rear surface plasmonic layer technique as a function of silicon cell thickness is discussed.

Keywords: Nanoparticles, Back Contact, High Efficiency, Antireflection coating

1 INTRODUCTION

In recent years, plasmonic particle layers (PPLs) made up of metal nanoparticles (MNPs) have been extensively studied as a way of improving solar cells [1,2,3]. Specific efforts have been made to incorporate Ag nanoparticles as Ag PPLs since Ag has relatively low absorbance in the wavelength range of interest [4]. Nanoparticles can efficiently scatter light [4,5,6] thereby increasing the optical path length of the incident light. Light coupling into the solar cell structure may be further enhanced if the PPL results in a high density of optical modes. It has already been proved that this technology enables an increase of the short circuit current (Jsc) in thin film technologies [7,8,9,10]. However, fabrication details make it perfectly suitable for traditional c-Si or mc-Si solar cells.

Nowadays, between 85% and 90% of the commercial solar cells are fabricated using crystalline silicon (c-Si) wafers. Its main cost is the wafer itself, so during the last 15 years the industrial trend has been to reduce the wafer thickness from 300 μm to 180 μm . In the near future the goal is to reduce it up to 50 microns [*]. However, the thinner the wafer is, the less red and near infrared (NIR) light is absorbed in the solar cell and a light trapping strategy is needed. In this case, texturing steps are not suitable: The thinner the wafer, the higher the breakage rate during processing and the greater the dependency of effective lifetimes on the surface recombination velocity. Thus, the use of plasmonics is not only suitable, but a promising substitute for texturing in next generation Si solar cells.

Moreover, the plasmonic effect can be used to inject light into silicon solar cells from diffuse sources, allowing silicon solar cell design for indoor applications [11].

The PPL integration, whether on the front or back surface of the solar cell, requires optimisation in order to maximize light scattering towards the bulk Si absorber layers. This work therefore sheds some light on different strategies of including an array of Ag NPs on a Si solar cell.

2 EXPERIMENTAL

The study is based on n-type interdigitated solar cells (IBC) fabricated by screen printing techniques [12]. The characterisation includes reflectivity and transmission optical measurements, and current-voltage (IV) and quantum efficiency (QE) opto-electronic characteristics. All IBC samples are first characterized with these techniques prior to the integration of Ag NPs.

The recipes to obtain suitable Ag NPs have previously been optimised during the LIMA project [13]. Briefly, different thicknesses of Ag have been evaporated on the cells. The self-aggregation is produced during a 1h annealing at temperatures between 200°C and 300°C in inert N₂ atmosphere and yields randomly distributed, hemispherical MNPs with a narrow range of diameters, see for instance Fig. 6.

In order to integrate Ag NPs within an ARC, the Ag NPs are encapsulated between a SiO_x layer deposited by PECVD and a SiO_x layer deposited by spin coating using a Hydrogen Silsesquioxane resist (HSQ). The thickness of this second layer is adjusted so that the total SiO_x thickness is 100nm. In this manner, a range of Plasmonic Antireflection Coatings (PARC) is obtained, as a function of the relative position of the Ag NPs inside the SiO_x ARC [14].

Table I: Pitch values for the IBC solar cells

	Group 1	Group 2
Pitch 1 (μm)	1400	1400
Pitch 2 (μm)	2200	2200

For the structure with the Ag NPs on the back, several pitches have been studied for two kinds of IBC solar cells in view of the risk of shunting the PN junction, as shown in Table I. In this case, an estimation of the increase of the short-circuit current that could be expected by the increase of the internal reflectance is obtained as:

$$\Delta J_{sc} = \frac{q}{h \cdot c} \int_{\lambda_0}^{\lambda_N} \Delta A(\lambda) \cdot \lambda \cdot IQE_0(\lambda) \cdot AM1.5G(\lambda) d\lambda \quad (\text{Eq.1})$$

where $\Delta A = (T_0 - T_{Ag}) - (R_{Ag} - R_0)$ is the increase in the absorption of light obtained from the reflectance (R) and transmission (T) spectra of the reference sample (subscript "0") and the sample with the Ag NPs (subscript "Ag"), q is the elemental charge of the electron, h is the Planck constant, c is the speed of light, λ is the wavelength, AM1.5G is the standard solar spectrum and IQE_0 is the Internal Quantum Efficiency (QE) of the Reference substrate.

The scattering properties of the array of Ag NPs are characterised with angular measurements using the experimental setup shown in Fig. 1. This uses a nanorotator NR360S from Thorlabs enabling accurate control the measurement angle, together with a collimated laser light source.

FIG.1 Schema of the angular measurement setup.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Integration in the front side of the cell

When Ag NPs are integrated directly on the front side of the cell, a decrease in reflectivity for longer wavelengths is found but also an increase for shorter wavelengths [15]. Similar results were found by Yang [16] (Fig. 2).

FIG.2 Ag NPs effect on EQE and Reflectivity when they are on the front side of a SiNx passivated solar cell.

When correcting External Quantum Efficiency (EQE) with reflectivity data (Fig. 3), the QE shows a significant loss that is explained primarily by Fano interference losses [17], as confirmed by the fact that the loss peak in the QE is asymmetrical. The enhancement for longer

wavelengths is then proved to be related with the reduction in reflectivity.

The final balance between the enhancement at longer wavelengths and the losses at shorter wavelengths do not show any enhancement in the short circuit current and thus in the efficiency of the solar cell.

FIG.3 Comparison of the Internal Quantum Efficiency of an IBC solar cell before and after including Ag NPs.

3.2 Integration within an Antireflection Coating (ARC)

One of the losses shown in Fig.1 is the increase of reflectivity in the range of wavelengths where the plasmonic resonance is expected to be [14]. Also, the optical properties of Ag NPs have been proved to be dependent to the distance to the Si [18]. For both reasons, a second set of samples of Ag NPs is integrated within a Plasmonic Anti-Reflection Coating (PARC), where the refractive index sequence is such as to reduce the overall light reflected by the Ag NPs at shorter wavelengths. It is furthermore possible to change the relative position of the Ag NPs within the ARC so that interference between incident and scattered waves can be optimised and losses to this end avoided.

Fig.4 proves that it is possible to reduce the overall reflectivity with this PARC. Fig. 5 shows that the intensity of the peak loss expected at shorter wavelengths can be reduced as the optical properties of the Ag NPs change. However, the Fano resonance remains a limiting loss mechanism in this case so there is no overall short circuit current enhancement.

FIG.4 (a) Reflectivity of different SiOx thicknesses as ARC on a polished Si wafer (b) Effect of the relative position of an array of Ag NPs within a 100nm SiOx ARC.

FIG.5 Internal Quantum Efficiency showing different losses related with the plasmonic resonance as consequence of the different Plasmonic Antireflection Coatings (PARC) where the Ag NPs have different optical properties.

3.2 Integration on the back side of the cell

In the case of Ag NPs on the back of the cell, the aim is to increase the optical path length for incident light by increasing the internal reflectivity. For this purpose, thicker Ag precursor layers have been used (up to 35nm). SEM images have been taken to verify that the self-aggregation was properly done, (Fig. 6).

FIG. 6 SEM images of the self-aggregated Ag NPs from 35nm precursor layer on a flat (left) and a textured (right) silicon solar cell passivated with SiNx.

Moreover, when putting the Ag NPs on the back side of the cell, any loss related with Fano interferences that may occur are avoided as short wavelengths are absorbed within Si before they interact with the Ag NPs. In the case of a 200 μ m Si wafer, only wavelengths above 900nm are not completely absorbed.

Fig. 7 shows the increase of light trapping in terms of absorption due to the addition of an array of Ag NPs on the back side of several IBC solar cells as detailed in Table I.

FIG. 7 Measured improvement in the light trapping in terms of the absorbance (1-Reflection-Transmission) for different IBC solar cells.

The estimation of the increase in the short-circuit current (Table II) is performed for different types of IBC solar cells and for different pitches with 35nm of Ag

precursor using Eq. 1. However, most samples show a decrease in shunt resistance, leading to lower efficiencies despite slight increases in short circuit current. The best results are obtained for the broader pitch as it is less affected by shunt currents (Table III).

Table II: Reference values and estimated enhancement due to the Ag NPs on the back side of the IBC solar cell.

	Group 1		Group 2	
	Pitch: 1	Pitch: 2	Pitch: 1	Pitch: 2
Jsc (mA/cm ²) ref	35.62	36.93	36.76	37.58
Δ Jsc (mA/cm ²)*	0.467	0.482	0.297	0.349

* From Eq 1

Table III: Best Jsc enhancement using Ag NPs on the back side of an IBC solar cell

	Jsc (mA/cm ²)	FF (%)	η (%)
Reference	37.58	73.37	17.55
Reference + Ag NPs	38.12	70.54	17.06

The use of a nanoparticle array instead of a flat back reflector is justified by the strong element of non-specular backscattering. This leads to increased light absorption and photocurrent generation. Angular measurements of reflectivity (from 0° to 90°) and transmission (from 90° to 180°) show that the scattering is enhanced by several orders of magnitude (Figure 8).

FIG. 8 Angular measurement at 1065nm of reflectivity (from 0° to 90°) and transmission (from 90° to 180°) for an array of Ag NPs at the front (Ag + Silicon) and at the back (Silicon + Ag) face of a 200 μ m polished Si wafer.

Fig. 8 shows that the light trapping is better when the array of Ag NPs is put on the back side of the solar cell. The wavelength used for this measurement being close to the band gap of Si, the structure has a low absorption coefficient in this wavelength range. It is in these circumstances of relatively low absorption when the higher light trapping enhancement is achieved with an increase in the back-scattering.

3.3 Simulating angular radiation pattern

We conclude with preliminary results from plasmonic particle scattering studies. We use a multiple scattering of radiation technique [19] to perform calculations assisting

in the assessment of measured optical spectra. This allows us to study regular particle arrays e. g. in a square or hexagonal lattice as well as random particle positions and sizes [20]. Various illumination conditions can be investigated, such as the influence of polarization, angle of incidence and the angular scattering at different wavelengths. In addition, the simulations enable the design of particle sizes and distributions in order to achieve optimal light trapping. In Fig. 9 we compare at different wavelengths the radiation scattering for two orthogonal light polarizations of a regular Ag NP sample that allows for strong particle coupling in case of p-polarized light, but does not indicate coupling effects in case of s-polarized light due to larger interparticle separations in this direction. This is shown not only by the overall enhanced light scattering in all directions for p-polarized light, but also by the increase (bumpy features) for low emission angles close to the surface plasmon resonance (SPR). Furthermore, operating at wavelengths beyond the SPR the increase in light trapping becomes independent of the light polarization. This phenomenological work will be developed further by applying the modeling techniques developed to particle distributions close to experimental samples.

FIG. 9 At different wavelengths and for two polarizations the angular-resolved radiation scattering is shown for a sample of Ag NPs in a rectangular lattice.

4 CONCLUSIONS

Ag NPs on the front of the cell lead to a reduced reflectivity at long wavelengths and an increased reflectivity at short wavelengths in the region of the plasmon resonance. This is observed for particles placed on the front surface of IBCs and for particles embedded in ARCs. This is because in both cases destructive Fano interferences occur and reduce the overall amount of light that can be absorbed in the IBC. When putting the Ag NPs on the back, this interference is rendered irrelevant as it only applies to light that is transmitted through the cell and lost in any case. In other words, the back surface geometry eliminates the Fano interference loss. The Ag NPs in this case act as an array of non-specular back-scattering centres. The present study is limited to investigating the effect of back surface Ag NPs on the short circuit current alone, however, since the introduction of shunt conduction paths for all samples with back surface Ag NPs has prevented the assessment of the fabricated devices in forward bias.

The overall conclusion from this work is with regards to cell thickness. We have demonstrated increases in photocurrent generation at long wavelengths where the IBC cell is not completely opaque to incident radiation, due to the decreasing Si absorption coefficient near the band-edge. At higher energies, however, the increase in optical path length afforded by the integration of Ag NPs cannot lead to any net advantage as the light is already completely absorbed.

These conclusions open further questions for future research. The first is the further development of experiments integrating Ag NPs on the rear surface and eliminating the process related shunt issues. The second is the systematic investigation of the advantage in improved light interaction as a function of cell thickness. Both will be developed further in studies of back surface Ag NPs integrated in c-Si solar cells as a function of cell thickness.

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